

Conversion of 3 to 6 : To a suspension of **3a, b** (0.01 mol) in pyridine (15 ml), benzenesulphonyl chloride (0.012 mol) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then kept at room temperature for several hours and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solids were crystallised from ethyl alcohol: **6a** (63%), $C_{17}H_{15}N_5O_6S$, m.p. 190° ; **6b** (68%), $C_{18}H_{17}N_5O_6S$, m.p. 210° .

α -N-Methyl derivatives (8a, b): To a cooled mixture of the *N*-hydroxymethyl derivatives¹ (**7a, b**; 1.0 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.0 ml), concentrated H_2SO_4 (10 ml) was added and then left to stand overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured onto ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: **8a** (55%), $C_{18}H_{21}N_5O_7$, m.p. 130° ; **8b** (64%), $C_{19}H_{23}N_5O_7$, m.p. 180° .

References

1. A. M. ISMAIEL, M. Y. YOUSIEF, M. A. METWALLY and M. M. EL-KERDAWY, *Indian J Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 1238.
2. M. A. METWALLY, M. Y. YOUSIEF, A. M. ISMAIEL and F. A. AMER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 54.
3. F. A. AMER, E. AFSAH, M. T. EL-ZIMAITY and M. A. METWALLY, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1979, **34**, 95.

Synthesis and Biological Activity of 1-(Substituted-anilinomalonyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-[substituted-azo]pyrazoles

V. S. JOLLY*, G. D. ARORA and PREETI TALWAR

Chemical Laboratories, Government Autonomous (Model) Science College, Gwalior

Manuscript received 14 June 1990, revised 9 October 1990, accepted 21 November 1990

ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES have been shown to possess various biological activities¹. In view of tuberculostatic activity² of hydrazides and diverse biological activities of pyrazoles the synthesis of new pyrazoles has been accomplished.

Treatment of acetylacetone with different diazonium salts in presence of sodium acetate gave 2,4-diketo-3-(substituted-azo)pentanes (**3**), which on reaction with malonanilic acid hydrazides³ (**4**) in glacial acetic acid medium gave new 1-(substituted-anilinomalonyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-[substituted-azo]pyrazoles (**5**) (Scheme 1).

Biological activities : Potentialities of compounds **5f, k, l, p** and **s** were evaluated for *in vitro* anti-HIV activity under developmental therapeutic programme AIDS involving plating of susceptible human 'host' cells. The growth inhibitory response of **1f** was poor (15.30%) whereas that of **5k, l, p** and **s** was 39.79, 40.52, 34.23 and 39.78% respectively, at dose levels tested.

*B-24, Gandhi Nagar, Gwalior-474 002.

Scheme 1

Four compounds **5a, e, f** and **i** were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using species of *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis*, *E. coli*, *Diplococcus-pneumoniae*. None of the products showed activity against the bacteria at $300 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by tlc. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Ir spectra were recorded in KBr.

2,4-Diketo(o-chlorophenylazo)pentane (3 ; R = Cl): *o*-Chloroaniline (12.7 g, 0.1 mol) was dissolved in aqueous hydrochloric acid (80 ml; 1:1). The contents were stirred and cooled ($0-2^\circ$), and a cold solution of sodium nitrite (12.0 g in 30 ml water) was slowly added to it maintaining the temperature between 0 to 2° .

The cold diazotised solution was then added dropwise to a well-cooled and stirred mixture of acetylacetone (10 ml) and sodium acetate (8.0 g dissolved in 10 ml of 50% aqueous ethanol). Stirring was continued for 1.5 h and the resulting yellow crystals were washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

2,4-Diketo-3-(phenylazo)pentane (3; R=H) and 2,4-diketo-3-(*o*-fluorophenylazo)pentane (3; R=F) were synthesised similarly (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula
1.	H	98	86.0	Golden yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂
2.	Cl	112	64.5	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂
3.	F	108	78.8	Pale yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

1-(Anilinomalonyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(*o*-chlorophenylazo)pyrazole (5j): 2,4-Diketo-3(*o*-chlorophenylazo)pentane (0.238 g, 0.001 mol) and maionanilic acid hydrazide (0.193 g, 0.001 mol) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 10 h. The resulting solid was purified by repeated washing with boiling acetic acid and crystallised as pale yellow crystals, (35.4%), m.p. 276° (Found: C, 60.74; H, 4.50; N, 17.80. C₂₀H₁₈ClN₅O₂ calcd. for: C, 60.75; H, 4.55; N, 17.69%). Other derivatives were obtained by the same procedure (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-ANILINOMALONYL-3,5-DIMETHYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED-AZO)PYRAZOLES (5)*

Compd no	R	R'	Molecular formula	M.p.* °C	Yield %
a	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₂	209	46.1
b	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	171	41.0
c	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	229	38.7
d	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	247	49.6
e	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	265d	32.7
f	H	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	237	30.3
g	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	234	44.4
h	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₅ O ₂	226	37.3
i	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₅ O ₂	277d	52.0
j	Cl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₅ O ₂	276d	35.4
k	Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ ClN ₅ O ₂	270d	48.8
l	Cl	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ ClN ₅ O ₃	265d	44.4
m	Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₂	262d	56.9
n	Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₂	264d	37.2
o	F	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ FN ₅ O ₂	278d	30.3
p	F	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ FN ₅ O ₃	260d	73.3
q	F	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ FN ₅ O ₃	134d	55.2
r	F	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ FN ₅ O ₃	261d	41.5
s	F	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClFN ₅ O ₂	258d	48.0
t	F	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClFN ₅ O ₂	272d	36.3

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis. **Solvent for crystallisation: Compounds a-i were crystallised from aqueous acetic acid and the rest were purified by repeated washing with hot acetic acid.

The pyrazole derivatives gave characteristic ir bands at 3 015 (CH aromatic), 2 960–2 870 (CH aliphatic), 1 670–1 620 (C=O, β -diketone), 1 595, 1 510, 1 460 (C=C), 1 540 (N=N), 1 470–1 370 (CH₃ bending) and 750 cm⁻¹ (monosubstituted benzene).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of National Cancer Institute, Maryland, U.S.A., for anti-HIV

activity testing and G. R. Medical College, Gwalior, for bacteriostatic studies, and feel indebted to the Director, D.R.D.E., Gwalior, for spectral analysis.

References

- H. G. GARG, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 446; H. G. GARG and V. ARORA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1972, **61**, 130; A. MUSTAFA, C. H. HISMAT, and M. M. J. YOUNIA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1970, **312**, 1011.
- COLEMAN, *Am. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1954, **69**, 1062.
- B. S. RATHORE and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 591.

Chemical Constituents and Antimicrobial Activity of *Achyranthes bidentata*†

G. BISHT* and H. SANDHU

Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University,
Nainital-263 002

and

L. S. BISHT

Health and Research Centre, Kumaun University, Nainital

Manuscript received 10 April 1989, revised 27 July 1990,
accepted 12 October 1990

ACHYRANTHES bidentata Blume (Fam: Amaranthaceae), native to temperate and sub-tropical Himalayas, occurs in Nainital upto 2500 m. The plant is also distributed in China, Java and Japan¹. The plant has got medicinal importance². We have investigated the alcoholic extract of the roots of plant for chemical constituents and antimicrobial activity, and the results are presented in this communication.

Experimental

The roots of the plant were collected from Nainital. The air-dried, powdered material (250 g) was extracted successively with petroleum ether and 90% ethanol in a Soxhlet for about 12 h. The ethanolic extract was cooled, filtered and concentrated. The concentrate ethanolic extract was then chromatographed on silica gel G tlc plates and/or Whatmann No. 1 or 3 papers. The developed chromatograms were inspected under uv light, sprayed with various reagents³ for different types of compounds and revealed the presence of amino acids, steroids triterpenoids, alkaloids and coumarins.

To find out the diet value of the plant with respect to amino acid content, the root extract was further investigated and free amino acids were determined^{4,5}. The concentrate ethanolic extract was analysed chromatographically employing Whatmann No. 1 or 3 papers (88.5 × 22.5"; 24 h at 18 ± 2°), silica gel G or cellulose layer (MN 300) as stationary phase and 1-butanol-acetic acid-water

†Paper presented in the 25th Annual Convention of Chemists, at Calcutta, 1988.